

Funded by
the European Union

This article has been submitted to WHISPERS 2024

Fuzzy Logic-Based Visualization and Interpretation of NDVI Maps

Mihai Ivanovici¹ Andrei Racoviteanu^{1,2}
Artur Kazak^{1,3} Nicolae Secrieru³

¹Electronics and Computers,
Transilvania University of Brasov, Brasov, Romania

²Applied Electronics and Information Engineering,
Politehnica University of Bucharest, Romania

³Space Technology Center,
Technical University of Moldova, Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

{mihai.ivanovici, artur.kazak}@unitbv.ro

andrei.racoviteanu@upb.ro, nicolae.secrieru@utm.md

Abstract

Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is widely-used for the monitoring of agriculture crops. Its interpretation is based on thresholds and the colormaps used for the visualization of NDVI maps are discrete. We propose a fuzzy logic approach for both the visualization and the interpretation of the NDVI maps. The rationale is that the NDVI values of agricultural crops exhibit a certain spread, while the interpretation based on thresholds is prone to a certain degree of incertitude. We define several membership functions for modeling three sub intervals of the NDVI values in the $[0,1]$ range, useful for the interpretation of the vegetation status for agricultural crops. The three sub intervals are corresponding to three categories of vegetation status: dried-out vegetation, moderately healthy and strongly developed. For a Sentinel-2 time series, we compare the visualization using the crisp logic, the Sentinel-2 color palette, and the color palettes resulting from the proposed membership functions implementing the fuzzy logic. We show that our colormap has a smoother color gradient, which can facilitate a more visually-appealing and interpretable transition of colors. We also show an example of inference for the interpretation of the NDVI values for an operational usage of the proposed fuzzy logic approach.

1 Introduction

One of the most important aspects of modern agriculture is the monitoring of agricultural crops, as it enables optimal assessment of plant health and

treatment, and eventually optimized production. In this regard, among the various technologies used, vegetation indices are a crucial tool. Being the most widely used vegetation index and obtained from data provided by different remote sensing devices [1], NDVI offers detailed information about plant health and density. The NDVI is calculated using the spectral reflectance of the red (RED) and near-infrared (NIR) bands, according to the formula:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - RED}{NIR + RED} \quad (1)$$

The index values range from -1 to +1. By analyzing NDVI values, we can identify regions with healthy, stressed, or dead vegetation. For example, NDVI values below 0 indicate water or artificial surfaces, values from 0 to 0.33 indicate dead vegetation or bare soil, values from 0.33 to 0.66 indicate stressed vegetation, and values from 0.66 to 1 indicate healthy vegetation, as described in Table 1 [2].

NDVI	interpretation
[-1, 0]	water/artificial surface
[0,0.33]	dried/dead/underdeveloped
[0.33, 0.66]	moderately healthy/developed
[0.66, 1]	very healthy/developed

Table 1: NDVI range and interpretation.

Based on optical data obtained from the Sentinel-2 satellite, specifically from the bands B4 (RED) and B8 (NIR) of the Sentinel-2 multi-spectral images, one can calculate the NDVI [3]. If hyper-spectral images are considered, for example, from the PRISMA mission, the NDVI can be computed using the closest wavelengths and strategies [4]. In situ measurements are also essential and can be performed with specialized instruments, e.g. an NDVI meter, in order to validate the satellite measurements. These measurements are typically used for validating and calibrating data obtained through remote sensing. In our practice, we have observed significant differences between NDVI values obtained through remote sensing and those obtained through in situ measurements, referring to both the average value and variability [5].

Dividing NDVI index values into categories of healthy, stressed, or dead vegetation often poses some difficulties, particularly in the case of index values like 0.33 or 0.66 – determining to which category to assign the value. When interpreting NDVI values, these moments of uncertainty can be overcome by using fuzzy logic. Utilizing logical functions and rules, fuzzy logic allows us to visualize and understand these data, determining the degree of truth in a statement. NDVI values can be interpreted through functions

that classify vegetation as *dry*, *stressed*, or *healthy* [6], and in the case of transition values, calculate the value of each function. Thus, we obtain a more precise picture of the vegetation state, avoiding errors in interpretation caused by fixed thresholds.

In analyzing NDVI index values, integrating fuzzy logic [7] enhances the precision, flexibility, and reliability of vegetation state evaluations. Moreover, we can combine fuzzy logic with traditional methods, such as remote sensing and in situ measurements, to obtain a more complete and coherent picture of the health of agricultural crops. Another possible use of fuzzy logic could be managing the spatial and temporal variations of NDVI values, allowing continuous and adaptive monitoring of vegetation state [8], and applying this method in remote sensing systems provides a valuable tool for managing agricultural resources and rapid intervention in case of crop stress or unfavorable climatic conditions [9].

In Section 2 we present our proposed approach based on two sets of membership functions (piece-wise linear and non-linear, respectively). In Section 3 we show some experimental results and in Section 4 we draw conclusions.

2 Proposed approach

We postulate two primary contributions in this paper: (i) in order to characterize the NDVI values into categories that are important to plant health programs, we establish two types of fuzzy membership functions to label NDVI values into 3 classes: robust vegetation, moderately healthy, dried out; (ii) we establish a more effective colormap that is derived from these fuzzy functions to enhance the visualization of the satellite images and in the same time to enable the inference, providing a given set of measurements for a particular agricultural crop or parcel.

2.1 Piece-wise linear approach

Figure 1 illustrates the initial piece-wise linear fuzzy membership function. We propose three equal constant regions and two transition zones between $[0.2, 0.4]$ and $[0.6, 0.8]$ that are situated within the $[0, 1]$ range of NDVI values. Deriving from it, we calculated the initial colormap variant based on the NDVI values. Consequently, the colors - expressed in RGB - of the constant regions were as follows: pure red $(1, 0, 0)$, pure yellow $(1, 1, 0)$, and pure green $(0, 1, 0)$ in that order. We required a color transition from red to yellow through orange for the initial transition zone. For this reason, the green plane was constructed using the ascending portion of the middle section (yellow in Figure 1). The red color was set to 1, while the blue color was set to 0. The red plane was used in the second transition by utilizing the descending portion of the middle section (yellow in Figure 1). The value

of green was set to 1, while blue was set to 0. A more clear transition is as follows: $RED(1, 0, 0) - ORANGE(1, \mu_{ylw-asc}, 0) - YELLOW(1, 1, 0) - LIGHT-GREEN(\mu_{ylw-desc}, 0, 0) - GREEN(0, 1, 0)$, where $\mu_{ylw-asc}$ is the ascending part of the yellow section while $\mu_{ylw-desc}$ is the descending part of the same function.

Figure 1: Membership functions - 1st approach.

The resulting colormap can be followed in Fig. 2(bottom). The primary issue in this instance was the color distribution along the NDVI values. The map contains an excessive number of yellow hues for NDVI values, which are associated with flourishing vegetation, in contrast to the Sentinel-2 colormap (Fig. 2 (top)). Additionally, the green hue of the developed vegetation is excessively smooth. The fields with thriving vegetation are nearly identical, which is not entirely accurate (Fig. 4 (bottom)). Note that various colormaps exist [4], but the Sentinel-2 is the most-commonly used.

2.2 Perceptual color space-based approach

Further on, we suggested the second variant of the fuzzy membership function (Fig.3), which includes non-linear variations. In order to be more closely aligned with the Sentinel-2 colormap, we also initiated the functions at -0.2, rather than 0. The transition in NDVI values for both fuzzy logic and colormap is now smoother due to the fact that the fuzzy functions are some parabola. The colormap that results can be observed in Fig. 2 (middle).

The process of obtaining the colormap from the second fuzzy proposal was no longer as straightforward as for the first attempt. This is due to the linear nature of the RGB color space and the non-linear nature of the second set of membership functions. In order to address this issue, we used the

Figure 2: Colormaps: Sentinel-2 colormap (top), parabola colormap (middle) and trapeze colormap (bottom).

CIE Lab Color Space to establish the colormap and subsequently returned to the RGB values for the final rendering. The chosen *CIE Lab* color space can be projected onto a sphere, which makes it simpler to create the desired colormap. We constructed a semicircle that was scaled within the NDVI values definition range of $[-0.2, 1]$ from dark red to dark green. The semicircle was generated by combining specified regions from the second fuzzy variant (Figure 7).

Then, the initial radius of the circle was extended to 50 to obtain the colors in Fig. 8 (left). However, it was observed that a constant value of L does not create the desired color transition. For this reason, the L variation was carried out as shown in Fig. 8(right). Because of the variation in the perceptual lightness component (L) across different hues, the function's form looks like the one in Fig.8(right). For example, the L difference between dark green and yellow is more pronounced than that between orange and dark red. Fig. 4 (middle) shows examples of images colored using the parabola colormap. It is evident that the hues are no longer homogeneous

Figure 3: Membership functions - 2nd approach.

over large areas like in the case of trapeze colormap and are more in line with Sentinel-2 ones. Last but not least, the *CIE Lab* color space is perceptually linear, which makes it a pertinent choice for the visual interpretations of the resulting NDVI maps.

The second application involved the statistical inference, i.e. estimating the probability of healthy vegetation based on the NDVI measurements for an agricultural crop or inside a specific parcel. We were able to describe a probability for each of the three vegetation classes — strongly developed, somewhat healthy, and dried out vegetation — with the direct use of fuzzy membership functions. The probability of interest is the intersection between the fuzzy membership functions and the NDVI histogram and has a mathematical definition as the following:

$$P_i = \frac{\int_{-0.2}^1 \mu_i H(x) dx}{\sum_{i=1}^3 \int_{-0.2}^1 \mu_i H(x) dx} \quad (2)$$

where μ_i is the fuzzy function for the vegetation classes, whereas $H(x)$ is the NDVI histogram of the analyzed culture.

Figure 4: Example of NDVI maps generated using: Sentinel-2 colormap (top), parabola colormap (middle) and trapeze colormap (bottom).

Figure 5: The wheat and lucerne fields chosen for comparison marked in black with blue rectangles (left), the two zoomed-in fields in Sentinel-2 colormap (middle) and with our proposed parabola colormap (right).

3 Experimental results

To validate the efficiency of the proposed method, namely the interpretation and visualization of NDVI maps using fuzzy logic, we conducted a series of experiments utilizing multi-spectral data from the Sentinel-2 satellite. We chose three representative dates from March, June and October 2023, sampling the typical season for agriculture in Romania. To compare the colormaps obtained through fuzzy logic with the Sentinel-2 color palette and with classic logic palettes, we applied the membership functions to the NDVI index data sets, generating colored maps for both variants of the fuzzy functions. We evaluated the results visually and numerically to determine the degree of conformity with the actual vegetation status (see Figure 2).

The first variant of the fuzzy functions generated a colormap with an excessive distribution of yellow shades, which did not adequately represent healthy vegetation. The second variant of the fuzzy functions produced a colormap with a smoother transition of NDVI values and a more realistic depiction of healthy vegetation. The generated images show that the second variant of the fuzzy functions provides a representation where the shades are no longer homogeneous over large areas (see Figure 4).

However, our suggested colormap is also more progressively than the Sentinel-2 one, which can be a clear advantage. Two fields, one containing

Figure 6: The NDVI Histogram for wheat and lucerne field .

wheat and the other lucerne, are shown in Fig. 5. Both are colored with the Sentinel variant and also our proposed solution. We should highlight that our proposed colormap has a better color gradient than Sentinel which proves to be useful in certain situations. For example, the difference between 0.49 and 0.51 from the perspective of vegetation is minor. However, these NDVI values are colored completely different in the Sentinel palette, which may cause a false alarm regarding the health of the culture. In our case, these kinds of issues are less common. The Sentinel-2 and trapezoidal maps provide a superior contrast for the region that is colored in red. This is due to the fact that the transitions are not as progressive. Nevertheless, this aspect is not particularly important, as our primary focus is on vegetation rather than uncultivated land.

Figure 7: The 2nd fuzzy function (left) and the parabola corresponding to the $a(b)$ dependency in Lab color space (right). On x-axis is the NDVI value, on y-axis is the probability

Figure 8: The ab semi circle in Lab color space (left) and the L component variation for every ab pair of the semi-circle (right).

Additionally, you can follow the NDVI histograms for the presented fields in Fig. 6. With orange is highlighted the NDVI histogram for wheat whereas the NDVI histogram for lucerne is marked with blue. For both cultures we computed the probability of each vegetation class using equation 2. The results may be seen in Table 2, for the case of using the parabola colormap. As it could be seen from Fig. 6 the lucerne field contains pixels from both strong and medium vegetation classes, the probabilities being more uniform. The Wheat field instead, has the majority of pixels clearly under the strong vegetation curve, reaching to a probability of more than 97%.

Class	Wheat field probability [%]
dried out	0
medium healthy	2.20
strong vegetation	97.79
Class	Lucerne field probability [%]
dried out	0
medium healthy	43.77
strong vegetation	56.22

Table 2: The fuzzy membership for the wheat and lucerne field in Fig. 6.

4 Conclusions

In this paper, we introduced a novel fuzzy logic-based interpretation for the NDVI values. In the initial scenario, we implemented a fuzzy membership function that was piece-wise linear in nature to establish the health of the vegetation. Because the linear variation is not so realistic we also created the second fuzzy membership functions containing parabola. By calculating the surface of the intersection between the histogram and fuzzy functions, we showed that it is possible to calculate, for any field that presents an NDVI histogram, the probability of belonging to one of the three classes of interest: strong vegetation, moderately developed and dried-out.

The proposed approach allows both the visualization of NDVI maps and the statistical inference of the analyzed agricultural field. In addition, we implemented a more efficient colormap that exhibits a more gradual color transition than the Sentinel colormap with the assistance of these functions. This would be very useful for a precision agriculture scenario, when variable rate irrigation or treatment are needed to be applied. We have demonstrated that this feature is beneficial when the NDVI values are close but they are located in distinct color intervals. Eventually, overall false alarms can be prevented in this manner.

Acknowledgment

Funded by the European Union. The AI4AGRI project entitled “Romanian Excellence Center on Artificial Intelligence on Earth Observation Data for Agriculture” received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under grant agreement no. 101079136.

**Funded by
the European Union**

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The work was partially funded by the project entitled "Satellite systems and platform for monitoring agricultural crops and aquatic surfaces using space technologies and drones", ID 020401.

References

- [1] Abdou Bannari, Daniel Morin, F Bonn, and A.R. Huete, "A review of vegetation indices," *Remote sensing reviews*, vol. 13, no. 1-2, pp. 95–120, 1995.
- [2] Mihai Ivanovici, Gheorghe Olteanu, Corneliu Florea, Radu-Mihai Coliban, Maria Ștefan, and Kamal Marandskiy, *Digital Transformation in Agriculture*, pp. 157–191, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024.
- [3] Rosa Lasaponara, Nicodemo Abate, Carmen Fattore, Angelo Aromando, Gianfranco Cardettini, and Marco Di Fonzo, "On the use of sentinel-2 ndvi time series and google earth engine to detect land-use/land-cover changes in fire-affected areas," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 14, no. 19, pp. 4723, 2022.
- [4] Ioana Cristina Plajer, A Băicoianu, Luciana Majercsik, and Mihai Ivanovici, "Ndvi computation from hyperspectral images," in *2023 13th Workshop on Hyperspectral Imaging and Signal Processing: Evolution in Remote Sensing (WHISPERS)*. IEEE, 2023, pp. 1–5.
- [5] Florea C. A. Kazak Ivanovici, M., "Statistical inference based on sentinel-2 and in situ ndvi measurements using montecarlo sampling," in *Proceedings of the International Symposium on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, Athens, Greece, 2024*.
- [6] Carmen Fucile, Danilo Cavaliere, and Sabrina Senatore, "A fuzzy tree-based framework for vegetation state monitoring," in *2022 IEEE Symposium Series on Computational Intelligence (SSCI)*, 2022, pp. 322–329.
- [7] L.A. Zadeh, "Fuzzy sets," *Information and Control*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 338–353, 1965.
- [8] Chen Xu and Zhang Yaping, "Land use change of china based on fuzzy classification and markov model," in *2011 Fourth International Symposium on Knowledge Acquisition and Modeling*, 2011, pp. 426–430.
- [9] S. Ding, C. M. Rulinda, A. Stein, and W. Bijker, "Ndvi time series and markov chains to model the change of fuzzy vegetative drought classes," in *2011 6th International Workshop on the Analysis of Multi-temporal Remote Sensing Images (Multi-Temp)*, 2011, pp. 201–204.